

Analysis of Maternal Near Miss Cases in a Tertiary Care CenterNalini I. Anand¹, Nita Rada², Mona D Gandhi³, Angi Shah⁴¹Professor and Head, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Shri M.P. Shah Govt. Medical College, Jamnagar, Gujarat^{2,3}Associate Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Shri M.P. Shah Govt. Medical College, Jamnagar, Gujarat⁴Second Year Resident, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Shri M.P. Shah Govt. Medical College, Jamnagar, Gujarat

Received: 25-07-2024 / Revised: 23-08-2024 / Accepted: 26-09-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Introduction:** Maternal near miss (MNM) cases involve severe complications during pregnancy, childbirth, or postpartum, where women survive life-threatening events due to timely medical interventions. These cases offer valuable insights into healthcare systems, revealing both successes and gaps in care, particularly in tertiary care settings that manage high-risk pregnancies.**Materials and Methods:** This retrospective observational study was conducted from July 2023 to July 2024 at Guru Gobind Singh Government Hospital (GGH), Jamnagar. A total of 280 MNM cases were analyzed based on the World Health Organization's (WHO) criteria, focusing on severe obstetric complications such as hemorrhage, hypertensive disorders, sepsis, and organ dysfunction. Data were collected from medical records, including patient demographics, clinical characteristics, interventions, and outcomes. Descriptive statistics were used for analysis, with significance evaluated at $p < 0.05$.**Results:** A total of 280 maternal near-miss (MNM) cases were analyzed. Multigravida women represented the largest group with 127 cases (45.36%), followed by second gravida (79 cases, 28.21%) and primigravida (74 cases, 26.42%). Hypertensive disorders, including preeclampsia and eclampsia, were the leading causes, accounting for 42.14% of cases, followed by severe anemia (18.57%) and obstetric hemorrhages such as APH (10.00%) and PPH (7.50%). Blood products were the most frequent intervention (82%), followed by uterine packing (8%) and laparotomy (4%). Most cases resulted in live births (77%), though adverse outcomes included 49 stillbirths (18%) and 15 cases (5%) involving ectopic pregnancies or abortions.**Conclusion:** Our study highlights that hypertensive disorders and severe anemia are major contributors to maternal near-miss cases, with timely interventions such as blood transfusions playing a critical role in positive outcomes. Despite most cases resulting in live births, the occurrence of stillbirths and other complications underscores the need for continuous improvements in maternal care.**Keywords:** Maternal near miss, hypertensive disorders, obstetric hemorrhage, maternal outcomes.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Maternal near miss (MNM) cases represent severe, life-threatening complications during pregnancy, childbirth, or the postpartum period, where women survive either by chance or due to timely, high-quality medical interventions. [1] These cases provide unique insights into healthcare systems, highlighting both areas of success and gaps in maternal care.

Unlike maternal mortality, which points to system failures, the analysis of MNM focuses on instances where life-saving measures worked, making it an essential tool for improving the quality of care. [2] MNM cases are also more frequent than maternal deaths, offering a broader scope for studying clinical practices and developing strategies to

prevent severe maternal outcomes. [3] Despite improvements in maternal mortality globally, maternal morbidity remains a significant public health challenge, especially in low- and middle-income countries. [4] According to the World Health Organization (WHO), nearly 830 women die daily from pregnancy-related complications, with many others surviving life-threatening conditions classified as MNM. [5]

In India, while the maternal mortality ratio (MMR) has decreased over recent years, MNM cases emphasize the continuing need for better care, particularly in high-risk pregnancies. [6] Tertiary care centers, which manage the most complicated referrals, play a pivotal role in addressing MNM

events. This study aims to identify the most common causes of MNM in such a setting and evaluate how interventions can be further improved to enhance maternal outcomes.

Materials and Methods

This study is a retrospective observational analysis conducted over a 12-month period, from July 2023 to July 2024, at Guru Gobind Singh Government Hospital (GGH), Jamnagar. The study aimed to identify the causes, interventions, and outcomes of maternal near miss (MNM) cases using the standardized criteria defined by the World Health Organization (WHO). As a tertiary care center, GGH receives referrals of high-risk pregnancies, making it an ideal setting to study MNM cases and evaluate maternal healthcare practices.

The study included 280 women diagnosed with severe pregnancy-related complications, meeting the WHO's MNM criteria. The included cases involved life-threatening conditions during pregnancy, childbirth, or the postpartum period, where timely medical interventions prevented maternal death. The WHO 2009 guidelines were followed to classify and analyze the cases based on clinical, laboratory, and management-related parameters.

Inclusion Criteria

- Pregnant women or women within 42 days postpartum diagnosed with life-threatening obstetric complications.
- Women meeting the clinical, laboratory, or management-based MNM criteria according to WHO 2009 guidelines (e.g., severe hemorrhage, hypertensive disorders, sepsis, or organ dysfunction).
- Cases referred from other healthcare facilities that required critical care or surgical intervention.

Exclusion Criteria

- Women with incomplete or missing medical records regarding key clinical variables.
- Cases where death occurred before the initiation of any life-saving intervention (i.e., not qualifying as MNM).

- Women with chronic conditions or comorbidities unrelated to pregnancy or postpartum complications.

Data were meticulously extracted from the Obstetrics and Gynecology Department's medical records at GGH. Key variables included patient demographics (age, parity, gestational age), clinical characteristics (mode of delivery, diagnosis at admission), and the nature of interventions (surgical procedures, ICU admissions, or blood transfusions). Hospital stay duration and final outcomes were also recorded. Each case was categorized using WHO's clinical, laboratory, and management-based MNM criteria, allowing for a thorough understanding of both the causes and outcomes of near miss events. Descriptive statistics were employed to analyze the collected data. Frequencies and percentages were used to summarize patient demographics, types of complications, and clinical outcomes. Associations between specific MNM causes and maternal outcomes were evaluated to identify patterns and areas for improvement in healthcare delivery. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant, indicating a meaningful association between the variables analyzed. The study adhered to institutional ethical guidelines, with approval obtained from the hospital's ethics committee. As the study involved retrospective data collection from medical records, patient consent was not required.

Results

A total of 280 maternal near miss (MNM) cases were analyzed during the study period. In our study, the distribution of maternal near-miss cases by gravida status shows that multigravida women constituted the largest group, with 127 cases (45.36%). This indicates that women with multiple pregnancies are at a higher risk of near-miss events. Second gravida cases followed, accounting for 79 cases (28.21%), while primigravida women, experiencing their first pregnancy, comprised 74 cases (26.42%). The leading causes of MNM were hypertensive disorders, such as preeclampsia and eclampsia, along with severe anemia and obstetric hemorrhages, including antepartum hemorrhage (APH) and postpartum hemorrhage (PPH). (Table 1)

Table 1: Causes for Maternal Near Miss (MNM)

Causes	Cases	% of Cases
PIH & Preeclampsia	118	42.14%
Eclampsia	32	11.42%
Antepartum Hemorrhage (APH)	28	10.00%
Postpartum Hemorrhage (PPH)	21	7.50%
Severe Anemia	52	18.57%
Ruptured Ectopic Pregnancy	8	2.80%
Uterine Rupture	2	0.70%
HELLP Syndrome with DIC	6	2.10%

Sickle Cell Anemia	4	1.40%
Diabetes Mellitus	4	1.40%
Thrombocytopenia with Bleeding	3	1.07%
Uterine Inversion	1	0.03%
Obstetric Hysterectomy	1	0.03%

In our study, the use of blood products was the most frequent intervention, accounting for 229 cases (82%), indicating its critical importance in management.

Uterine packing was employed in 23 cases (8%), while laparotomy was performed in 12 cases (4%).

Other miscellaneous interventions were used in 16 cases (6%). Less frequent interventions included hysterotomy and inotrope support, each utilized in 7 cases (3%).

Hysterectomy and hemodialysis were rarely required, with only 1 case (0%) each. (Figure 1)

Figure 1: Distribution of Interventions (%)

In our study, the outcomes show that the majority of cases resulted in live births, accounting for 216 cases (77%), indicating a positive outcome in most pregnancies. However, there were 49 cases (18%) of stillbirth, reflecting a significant number of

adverse outcomes. Additionally, 15 cases (5%) were categorized under others, including ectopic pregnancies and abortions, representing a smaller but important fraction of outcomes with complications or pregnancy loss. (Figure 2)

Figure 2: Outcome of study subjects (%)

Discussion

In our study, the majority of maternal near-miss (MNM) cases involved multigravida women (45.36%), followed by second gravida (28.21%) and primigravida women (26.42%). This trend aligns with findings from Roopa et al. [7], where hemorrhage and hypertensive disorders significantly affected multipara women, highlighting the cumulative risks of multiple pregnancies. Similarly, Gupta et al. [8] observed that multigravida women experienced higher near-miss rates, which they attributed to delays in seeking care and pre-existing complications from previous pregnancies. These studies underscore that women with multiple pregnancies are at greater risk of developing life-threatening conditions, often due to repeated obstetric complications or inadequate birth spacing. In contrast, Rulisa et al. [9] reported a higher incidence of MNM among primipara women, linking this to hypertensive disorders such as preeclampsia and eclampsia. This discrepancy with our findings may reflect variations in antenatal care quality and access to healthcare across different regions. Mansuri and Mall [10] further emphasized that multigravida women remain vulnerable to hemorrhagic complications, while primigravida cases face higher risks from hypertensive conditions. These patterns suggest that tailored healthcare interventions focusing on early detection of hypertensive disorders in first-time pregnancies and improved management of obstetric hemorrhage in multipara women can significantly improve maternal outcomes.

In our study, the leading cause of MNM cases was preeclampsia and PIH (42.14%), followed by eclampsia (11.42%). This aligns with findings from Gupta et al. [8], who also reported hypertensive disorders, including preeclampsia, as a dominant contributor to MNM, reflecting poor control of blood pressure during pregnancy and delayed intervention in many cases. Similarly, Rulisa et al. [9] found that hypertensive diseases, especially eclampsia, were among the top causes of severe maternal morbidity in low-resource settings, contributing to nearly 28.6% of their near-miss cases. Additionally, Mansuri and Mall [10] noted that eclampsia and preeclampsia accounted for almost 55% of life-threatening maternal conditions, underscoring the critical need for early diagnosis and management of hypertensive disorders to prevent adverse outcomes.

Our data also revealed that severe anemia (18.57%) and hemorrhagic events, including APH (10.00%) and PPH (7.50%), were significant causes of MNM. Roopa et al. [7] highlighted similar trends, identifying hemorrhage as a leading cause of near-miss cases, particularly postpartum hemorrhage, which can rapidly lead to hemodynamic collapse if

untreated. Tallapureddy et al. [11] emphasized that timely blood transfusion and access to surgical interventions are essential for managing hemorrhagic events, as such conditions can escalate quickly if left unaddressed. Moreover, our findings on ruptured ectopic pregnancy (2.8%) and uterine rupture (0.7%) correspond with those from Oğlak et al. [12], where obstetric complications like rupture required immediate surgical attention to prevent mortality.

In our study, the most frequent intervention was the use of blood products (82%), underscoring the critical role of timely transfusion in managing life-threatening conditions such as hemorrhage. This aligns with findings by Gupta et al. [8], who emphasized that blood transfusion was crucial in cases of severe postpartum hemorrhage, a leading cause of MNM, as it prevented hypovolemic shock and further complications. Similarly, Roopa et al. [7] reported high reliance on blood product use for hemorrhagic conditions, including antepartum and postpartum hemorrhages, reinforcing the importance of blood availability in emergency obstetric care. Oğlak et al. [12] further highlighted that prompt transfusion improves outcomes and reduces maternal mortality rates in women with obstetric hemorrhage.

Our study also showed that uterine packing (8%) and laparotomy (4%) were employed in critical cases to control bleeding, in line with findings from Rulisa et al. [9], who found that surgical interventions such as laparotomy were essential for managing uterine rupture and severe hemorrhagic events. Tallapureddy et al. [11] noted similar patterns, stating that surgical procedures like laparotomy or hysterectomy are often required when conservative measures fail to control bleeding. Additionally, our use of hysterotomy and inotrope support (3%) matches the findings from Mansuri and Mall [10], who reported these interventions in critical cases involving uterine rupture or severe anemia where aggressive management was needed to stabilize patients. These interventions highlight the need for both medical and surgical strategies in MNM management, demonstrating that comprehensive care—including timely blood transfusion, conservative packing, and invasive procedures—plays a pivotal role in improving maternal outcomes across healthcare settings.

In our study, live births accounted for 77% of the cases, reflecting favorable outcomes for most pregnancies despite the life-threatening complications encountered. This aligns with Gupta et al. [8], who reported a high proportion of live births among MNM cases, attributing it to prompt medical interventions such as blood transfusions and surgical procedures that stabilized patients in critical conditions. Similarly, Rulisa et al. [9] noted

a majority of live births in their cohort, although they emphasized the importance of tertiary care referral systems in ensuring positive outcomes despite the severe morbidities experienced. These findings indicate that comprehensive obstetric care, especially in tertiary settings, plays a vital role in achieving successful deliveries even in high-risk cases.

However, our study also recorded 49 stillbirths (18%), highlighting the significant burden of adverse pregnancy outcomes. This trend is consistent with Roopa et al. [7], who identified stillbirths as a common outcome in cases of severe obstetric complications, particularly when conditions such as preeclampsia, hemorrhage, or infections were not managed promptly. Mansuri and Mall [10] similarly emphasized the impact of delayed healthcare access and referral on stillbirth rates among MNM cases. The remaining 5% of cases in our study involved ectopic pregnancies and abortions, reflecting the complexities of managing early pregnancy complications. Tallapureddy et al. [11] observed that such cases often required urgent surgical intervention to prevent maternal deterioration. These findings underscore the need for timely and effective obstetric care to mitigate pregnancy loss and improve maternal and fetal outcomes in cases of severe maternal morbidity.

A key limitation of our study is the single-center design, which may limit the generalizability of our findings to other healthcare settings with different resource levels and patient demographics. Additionally, retrospective data collection could introduce bias, as complete clinical information might not always be available, and delays in seeking care were not systematically captured.

Conclusion

Our study emphasizes the importance of timely and effective interventions in managing maternal near-miss cases, demonstrating that comprehensive care can lead to favorable outcomes despite severe complications. The predominance of live births reflects the success of medical and surgical strategies, though the occurrence of stillbirths and other adverse outcomes highlights ongoing challenges. A multidisciplinary approach, focusing on early detection, prompt intervention, and continuous monitoring, is essential for improving both maternal and fetal outcomes. Strengthening antenatal care and ensuring the availability of critical resources remain pivotal in reducing the risks associated with high-risk pregnancies and severe maternal morbidities.

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